

Syntheses of 2H, 6H-Pyrano (3, 2-b) and 2H, 12H - Pyrano (2, 3-a) phenoxazin-2-ones

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Some nitro pyranophenoxazin-2-ones have been synthesised by the condensation of halogeno-nitro-benzenes with 6-amino- and 8-amino-7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarins.

Phenoxazine derivatives exhibited marked antitubercular,⁸ antibacterial,⁴ tumor retarding,⁵ sedative,⁶ hypotensive⁷ and radio protective⁸ properties. Biological activities of coumarins are also well known.⁹

It, therefore, seemed to be of interest to synthesise compounds, having fused phenoxazine and α -pyrone rings, from the point of view of biological activity.

Pyranophenoxazin-2-ones have been prepared by refluxing equimolecular quantities of amino hydroxy-coumarins and halogeno-nitro-benzenes, in ethanolic solution in presence of sodium acetate. These are shining brilliantly coloured compounds. In this way pyranophenoxazin-2-ones from 6-amino- and 8-amino-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins were obtained by condensing them with a number of halogeno-nitrobenzenes viz., 1-chloro-2, 6, dinitro -1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-, 1-chloro-2, 6, dinitro-4-methyl, 1-chloro-2, 4, 6-trinitro-5 methyl-, 1, 2, 3-trichloro-4, 6-dinitro-, 1, 4-dichloro-2, 6-dinitro-, 1, 2, 5-trichloro-4, 6-dinitro-, 1, 2-dichloro-4, 6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1, 4-dibromo-2, 6-dinitro- and 1, 4-dichloro-2, 6-dinitro-5-methyl benzenes. 6-Amino- and 8-amino-7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarins were obtained by the reduction of corresponding nitrocoumarin by sodium hydrosulphite.

During the course of this work it was observed that the formation of pyranophenoxazin-2-ones did not take place unless both the ortho positions in the halogeno-nitrobenzenes are substituted¹⁰. Thus 1-chloro-2, 4-dinitro-, 1, 3-dichloro-4, 6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-4, 6-dinitro-3-methyl-, 1, 4-dichloro-2-nitro- and 1, 3-dibromo-4, 6-dinitro-5-methyl-benzenes gave only uncyclised anilino-7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin derivatives, under the usual experimental conditions. It was also noted that when

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the reactive halogen had a nitro group and a halogen atom in its *ortho* positions, the cyclisation always took place by elimination of halogen atom in preference to the nitro group¹¹, since 1, 2-dichloro-, 1-chloro-2-bromo-, or 1-chloro-2-iodo-4, 6-dinitrobenzenes furnished with 6-amino-7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin, 7, 9-dinitro-4-methyl-2H, 6H-pyrano (3, 2-b) phenoxazin-2-one, identical to that obtained by 1-chloro-2, 4, 6-trinitrobenzene.

In the halogeno-nitrobenzenes which are unsymmetrically substituted and have two nitro groups in *ortho* positions of the reactive halogen atom, though two products are expected depending upon the possibility as to which nitro group is involved, only one could be isolated, involving the elimination of the nitro group adjacent to the methyl group¹². With 1-chloro-2, 4, 6-trinitro-5-methylbenzene and 6-amino-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, 4, 10-dimethyl-7, 9-dinitro-2H, 6H-pyrano (3, 2-b) phenoxazin-2-one was obtained. The structure follows from the formation of different compounds by the condensation of 1, 2-dichloro-4, 6-dinitro-5-methyl- and 1-chloro-2, 4, 6-trinitro-5-methyl-benzenes with 6-amino-7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin.

EXPERIMENTAL*

General method for the preparation of pyranophenoxazin-2-ones: To a solution of halogeno-nitrobenzene (0.01 mol) and *ortho* amino-hydroxycoumarin (0.01 mol) in ethenol was added sodium acetate solution (10 ml, 2N) under stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs on water bath. After cooling, the pyranophenoxazin-2-one was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid. They are reported in Tables I and II.

TABLE I
Substituted 2H, 6H,-pyrano (3, 2-b) phenoxazin-2-ones

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Formula	M. P.	% Yield	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		% Nitrogen	
							Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	H	H	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₅	281°	82	61.97	61.93	3.10	3.22	9.12	9.03
2.	H	NO ₂	H	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₂ O ₇	>300°	85	54.28	54.08	2.42	2.53	11.70	11.83
3.	H	CH ₃	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₅	>300°	75	62.98	62.96	3.1	3.7	8.73	8.64
4.	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₇	265°	85	55.35	55.28	2.82	2.98	11.25	11.38
5.	Cl	NO ₂	H	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₂ O ₇ Cl	267°	84	49.20	49.29	2.18	2.05	11.59	11.39
6.	H	Cl	H	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	298°	80	55.82	55.73	2.52	2.61	8.00	8.12
7.	H	NO ₂	Cl	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₂ O ₇ Cl	280°	82	49.32	49.29	2.12	2.05	11.50	11.39
8.	H	NO ₂	CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₇	260°	83	55.35	55.28	3.00	2.98	11.30	11.38
9.	H	Br	H	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ Br	>300°	75	66.67	66.66	3.41	3.33	7.90	7.78
10.	CH ₃	Cl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	278°	80	56.92	56.90	3.15	3.07	7.89	7.81

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* All melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE II

Substituted 2*H*, 12*H*-pyrano (2, 3-*a*) phenoxazin-2-ones

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Formula	M. P.	% Yield	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		% Nitrogen	
							Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	H	H	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₅	277°	75	62.05	61.93	3.29	3.22	9.20	9.03
2.	H	NO ₂	H	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₂ O ₇	>300°	80	54.28	54.09	2.40	2.53	12.00	11.83
3.	H	CH ₃	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₅	>300°	80	63.04	62.96	3.56	3.70	8.63	8.64
4.	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₇	270°	90	55.10	55.28	3.00	2.98	11.40	11.38
5.	Cl	NO ₂	H	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₂ O ₇ Cl	263°	85	49.36	49.29	2.16	2.05	11.41	11.39
6.	H	Cl	H	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	280°	75	55.80	55.73	2.72	2.61	8.19	8.12
7.	H	NO ₂	Cl	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₂ O ₇ Cl	267°	72	49.20	49.29	2.00	2.05	11.29	11.39
8.	H	NO ₂	CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₇	265°	82	55.37	55.28	2.90	2.98	11.28	11.38
9.	H	Br	H	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ Br	>300°	70	66.70	66.66	3.42	3.33	7.88	7.78
10.	CH ₃	Cl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	271°	85	56.98	56.90	3.17	3.07	7.80	7.81

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